

A new combination in *Semenovia* (Apiaceae)

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Abstract: *Platytaenia schischkinii* Kamelin is formally transferred to *Semenovia* Regel & Herder based on the current circumscription that treats *Neoplatytaenia* Geld. (\equiv *Platytaenia* Nevski & Vved., *nom. illeg.*) as a synonym of *Semenovia*.

Keywords: *Neoplatytaenia*, *Platytaenia schischkinii*, Tajikistan

Introduction

The genus *Semenovia* Regel & Herder comprises 33 species distributed from Iran to Central Asia and China (POWO, 2025). Under the current circumscription, *Neoplatytaenia* Geld. (\equiv *Platytaenia* Nevski & Vved., *nom. illeg.*) is treated as a synonym of *Semenovia* (Kubitzki 2018). Accordingly, *Platytaenia schischkinii* Kamelin is here formally transferred to *Semenovia*.

New combination

Semenovia schischkinii (Kamelin) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

\equiv *Platytaenia schischkinii* Kamelin, Fl. Ushchel. Reki Varzob 272. 2021.

Holotype: Tajikistan, Varzob, upper part of Maichura river, *R.V. Kamelin s.n.* (TAD).

Distribution: Endemic to Tajikistan.

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References

- Kubitzki, K. (2018). Apiaceae. In: Kubitzki, K. and Bittrich, V. (eds.), The families and genera of flowering plants, Vol. 15: 9–206. Springer Verlag, Berlin & Heidelberg.
- POWO. (2025). Plants of the World Online. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Available from: <http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/> (accessed 25 August 2025).